

A Study on Passengers Satisfaction towards Transport Services of TNSTC Buses

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Abstract

The aim of this study is to figure out what factors are most important in explaining different level of satisfaction concerning passengers with regard to Transport Corporation, Problem faced by such passengers and to provide suggestions to overcome the problems. The state road transport undertakings have a place of prominence in the road transport sector. They perform very vital road in the daily life of millions of our country. The STUs carried (satisfaction, there financial position of STU in India had been for from satisfactory).

Introduction

Transportation moves people and goods from one place to another using a variety of vehicles across different infrastructure systems. It does this using not only technology (namely vehicles, energy, and infrastructure), but also people's time and effort, producing not only the desired outputs of passenger trips and freight shipments, but also adverse outcomes such as air pollution, noise, congestion, crashes, injuries, and fatalities.

Meaning of Transportation

Transport (British English) or transportation (American English) is the movement of people and goods from one place to another. The term is derived from the Latin *trans* ("across") and *portare* ("to carry").

Statement of the Problem

Transport sector occupies a place of pivotal importance in Indian economy. The tremendous growth in transport sector has expanded trade, commerce and industries phenomenally. Technological advancement has resulted in newer vehicles with advanced features in the buses. Burgeoning gap between expectation of passengers and existing level of facilities and convenient offered in the buses have a definite bearing on the service quality in transport sectors. The present study seeks to explore what the passengers using public transport corporation in Dharmapuri District perceive in general and in specific about the various aspects of the services provided by the corporation in particular.

In other words, the entire study explores whether transport corporation in Dharmapuri district measuring passenger satisfaction and if not what problems under the corporation in Dharmapuri from providing quality services. This is the research problem pursued in the study.

Need and Importance of the Study

Movement of the people from one place to another place and the increase in population resulted in heavy demand for quick, efficient transport service. Under these circumstances, there is every possibility for determination of the quality of services provided bus transportation industries because of heavy competition. TNSTC have to provide better service because it is a questionnaire of survival for them. The importance of the study is to find out answer for the questions.

Objectives of the Study

- To measure the level of satisfaction of passengers of Tamil Nadu state transport corporation ltd. Dharmapuri.(D.T)
- To analyze the problems faced by the passengers' of Tamil Nadu state transport corporation ltd.

Limitation of the Study

The researcher focuses and collects the data only from the respondents who are able to understand and to give their answers for the questions asked for this research work.

The study only based on passengers satisfaction.

Sources of Data

For the research purpose both the data are collected. Primary data as well as secondary data.

Primary data

Primary data is fresh data first hand information collected by way of questionnaire from the respondents.

Secondary data

Secondary data is second hand information already collected someone else information gathered through books Journals, magazines, reports, newspapers and various websites.

Review of Literature

UK Department for Transport (2003)¹⁵ has also conducted its study regarding customer need toward public transport. High frequency of service, reliable services and reasonable fares which offer value for money are revealed as important needs of UK public transport users. The bus should also have a broad range of destinations to fulfill travel-related demand of customers.

In this study, the users also reported the importance of understandable time schedule information in bus stop and in local newspaper to make them aware of existing available services. Simple ticket booking arrangements or mode of reservation are also important in order to make them avail public transportation services.

Gunaseelan G. (1996)¹⁹ in this article "Public Bus Transport Services in Tamilnadu – An Appraisal". The process of nationalization of passenger road transport services in Tamilnadu goes back to the period immediately after the Independence of India. Perhaps Tamilnadu has been one of the pace setting States in India to nationalize road transport services in the country. The Madras city bus services were the first to be nationalized in Tamilnadu in July 1948 and thus in the year 1997 it will be completing 50 years of bus transport service to the travelling public in the region. With the economic liberalization and privatization programmes in India there is a great debate over the tradeoff between the commercial objective and the social service goal of State Transport

Undertakings (STUs). In the changing economic scenario it is felt necessary to make a detailed study of the performance of the Road Transport Corporations (RTCs) in Tamilnadu.

TNSTC Transport an Overview

Tamil Nadu State Transport Corporation Limited (TNSTC) is a public transport bus operator in Tamil Nadu, India. It operates intercity bus services to cities within Tamil Nadu, and from Tamil Nadu to its neighbouring states with a combined fleet strength of 22203 buses as of 2016-17. It also operates Public transport bus service in many cities of Tamil Nadu, with the exception of Chennai, where the public bus service is operated by MTC, and a subsidiary of TNSTC

Tamil Nadu State Transport Corporation

Founded: 1972

No. Board of Directors: 7

Functions: The functions of Tamil Nadu State Transport Corporation is exclusively for operating long distance express services connecting all the district Headquarters in the State (Tamil Nadu).

Services: Deluxe Buses, Ultra Deluxe Buses, AC Buses, Volvo Buses

Tamil Nadu State Transport Corporation issues online applications to fill various vacancies. Those Candidates who are interested are supposed to fill those applications and submitting them through online mode before the last date ends.

Respondents Opinion Regarding Satisfaction of TNSTC Bus Schedule

S.No.	Satisfaction	No. of Respondents	Percentage %
1	Very satisfied	97	32
2	Somewhat satisfied	116	39
3	Somewhat dissatisfied	39	13
4	Dissatisfied	48	16
Total		300	100

Source: Primary data

Interpretation

Thus the above the table 4.8 shows that 32%of the respondents are very satisfied and 39% of the respondents are somewhat satisfied and 13% of the respondents are somewhat dissatisfied and 16% of the respondent are dissatisfied. Majority (39%) of the respondents are somewhat satisfied about TNSTC Bus service schedule.

Respondents Opinion Regarding Satisfaction of TNSTC Bus Schedule

Source: Primary Data

Findings

- Majority (54%) of the respondents are female
- Majority (47%) of the respondents are belonged to the age group between of 21-40 years.
- Majority (51%) of the respondents are married.
- Majority (26%) of the respondents are Business man.
- Majority (24%) of the respondents are earning annual income of Rs.50,000 to Rs.1,00,000
- Majority (26%) of the respondents are once in a week travel by bus
- Majority (39%) of the respondents are regularly travel by bus for working place
- Majority (39%) of the respondents are somewhat satisfied about Bus service schedule of TNSTC
- Majority (38%) of the respondents are mostly using local (or) town bus.
- Majority (31%) of the respondents are somewhat dissatisfied about satisfaction of TNSTC Bus service Routes.
- Majority (68%) of the respondent are said convenient while travelling in TNSTC bus service
- Majority 61% of the respondents are said TNSTC provide special buses for student, women and senior citizen.
- Majority (33%) of the respondents are said sometimes over crowded in TNSTC buses.
- Majority (64%) of respondents are said TNSTC not providing nonstop from majestic to major destinations.
- Majority (64%) of respondents are said need improvement of behavioral conduct of drivers and conductors
- Majority (44%) of the respondents are said major problem of TNSTC bus transport is traffic.
- Majority (36%) of the respondents are strongly agree regarding internal space and sitting arrangement in TNSTC Buses Very convenient.
- Majority (51%) of the respondents are said high price is charged in TNSTC Buses.
- Majority (67%) of respondents are said right location for Dharmapuri bus stand is providing bus service facilities.
- Majority (51%) of the respondents are said TNSTC providing express time table through SMS to passengers.
- Majority (63%) of the respondents are said TNSTC bus free for school and college students.
- Majority 50% of the respondents are getting Bus timing information from TNSTC information centre.
- Majority (64%) of respondents are said online facilities available in TNSTC bus service.
- Majority (52%) of the respondents said correct time buses arrival on stage.
- Majority (68%) of the respondents are said maintenance of TNSTC buses are good conditions.
- Majority (52%) of the respondents are said TNSTC provide special buses for festival time.
- Majority (51%) of the respondents are told first aid box is available in TNSTC bus.

Suggestions

- After analysing of data find out the result based on the result offer some suggestion to improve the passengers satisfaction of TNSTC Ltd., in dharmapuri district. It as given below.
- There should be uniformity in the frequency of buses for different place.
- Proper maintenance of buses and bus stands should be required to retain the existing and attracting the new passengers for the survival of transport industries in the long run.
- All buses can have radio/ music system or provision for video to be played. So that the passengers don't feel the stress & strain while travelling.

- First aid facilities have to be made both in bus stations and in buses. The first aid boxes need to have general medicines which have to be checked and if medicines expire, they to be replaced with new ones.
- The time table boards showing timings of arrivals and departures of buses should be prominently displayed and corrected when ever required. The boards should be clear and legible, simple and precise to see, so that there will be no confusion to passengers.
- Additional security personnel have to be deployed at all key junctions and at place where there is more of passenger traffic.
- The conductors need to bring more “coins /change” to return to the passengers then and there instead of using abusive words.

Conclusion

A good Public Transport System must be easy, fast, safe and also affordable. Tamil Nadu has a well-established transportation system which connects all parts of the state. The bus fare in Tamil Nadu is the lowest among all the various states in the country. The present study revealed the level of satisfaction of passengers on information about bus routes and timings. However, most of them have either moderate or low level of satisfaction towards the services of TNSTC. Maintenance of buses, efficient crews and congenial relationship with the passengers were the main requirements to promote the level of satisfaction of passengers towards the services of TNSTC.